

Chlorine Derivatives of Mixed Amine Molybdenum Tricarbonyls

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Manuscript received 5 May 1978, revised 8 June 1979, accepted 26 July 1980

[(L-L)(Am)Mo(CO)₃Cl]Cl₂ derivatives of Mo(II) and non-ionic (L-L)(Am)MoCl₄ complexes of Mo(IV) have been prepared by chlorine oxidation of (L-L)(Am)Mo(CO)₃ (where, L-L = *o*-phen or 2,2'-bipy and Am = monodentate amines). Structures of the complexes have been proposed on the basis of elemental analysis, magnetic moment, molar conductance and infrared spectra.

IN view of the interesting behaviour of mixed amine molybdenumtricarbonyls (L-L)(Am)Mo(CO)₃, towards iodine¹ and bromine^{2,3} it was considered of interest to study their chlorine oxidation reactions. These reactions have now been investigated and some new complexes of the general formula [(L-L)(Am)Mo(CO)₃Cl]Cl₂ and (L-L)(Am)MoCl₄ (where, L-L = *o*-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridyl and Am = butylamine, *n*-hexylamine, cyclohexylamine, benzylamine, piperidine or morpholine) have been isolated and characterized.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade and reactions were performed under dry nitrogen atmosphere. Hexacarbonylmolybdenum(O) was sublimed before use. Mixed amine molybdenum tricarbonyls were prepared by the methods reported in literature⁴. Infrared spectra (4000-1200 cm⁻¹ region) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer model 337, in KBr discs. Magnetic moment measurements were made at room temperature by Faraday's method and molar conductance of the compounds were determined in nitrobenzene with the help of a Systronic conductivity bridge model 305. Chlorine was estimated gravimetrically by precipitation as silver salt.

Preparation of monochloro-o-phenanthroline (butylamine) tricarbonyl molybdenum(II) Trichloride, [(C₁₂H₈N₂)(C₄H₉NH₂)Mo(CO)₃Cl]Cl₂: Chlorine swept benzene (prepared by passing a slow stream of gaseous chlorine through 20 ml benzene for 10 minutes) was added dropwise on to solid *o*-phenanthroline (butylamine) tricarbonyl molybdenum(O) (0.15 g) at ambient temperature under dry nitrogen with constant stirring of the reaction mixture. Effervescence of carbon-monoxide was observed and black colour of the solid carbonyl turned golden-yellow. After 2 hr, when effervescence ceased, stirring was stopped and yellow supernatant liquid decanted and preserved under nitrogen. Residue was washed with benzene and dried *in vacuo*.

Other [(L-L)(Am)Mo(CO)₃Cl]Cl₂ complexes were similarly prepared. Reaction conditions and

analytical data of the derivatives are given in Table 1.

Preparation of tetrachloro-o-phenanthroline (butylamine) molybdenum(IV), [(C₁₂H₈N₂)(C₄H₉NH₂)MoCl₄]: Yellow supernatant liquid obtained in the above mentioned reaction was poured to an excess of hexane (*ca.* 75 ml) from which yellow compound precipitated. It was filtered off and washed with hexane to remove traces of chlorine (if any). The residue was dried *in vacuo*.

Other (L-L)(Am)MoCl₄ complexes were similarly isolated. Physical characteristics and analytical data of the derivatives are given in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

Treatment of mixed amine molybdenum tricarbonyls, (L-L)Am(Mo)(CO)₃ with a chlorine solution at ambient temperature yielded chlorocarbonyl products, [(L-L)(Am)Mo(CO)₃Cl]Cl₂ and non-carbonyl products, (L-L)(Am)MoCl₄. Due to rapid decomposition of (L-L)(Am)Mo(CO)₃ derivatives in solution, they were used as solids for chlorination purpose.

[(L-L)(Am)Mo(CO)₃Cl]Cl₂ complexes were shining-grey to golden-yellow coloured crystalline solids, soluble in polar solvents such as acetone, tetrahydrofuran, dimethylformamide, alcohols, chloroform, dichloromethane and nitrobenzene. Although stable under dry nitrogen, they were air and moisture sensitive and slowly decomposed in solution. Instability of the complexes in solution prevented their recrystallization. However, complete solubility of the chlorinated products in tetrahydrofuran indicated that they were free from unreacted parent carbonyls[†]. On heating in sealed capillary tubes, they first decomposed to light yellow products (unidentified) which on further heating changed to black masses and melted at high temperature.

Infrared spectra of [(L-L)(Am)Mo(CO)₃Cl]Cl₂ derivatives exhibited three strong carbonyl bands in

† Mixed amine molybdenum tricarbonyls are insoluble in tetrahydrofuran.

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TABLE 1—REACTION CONDITIONS AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF [(L-L)(Am)Mo(CO)₃Cl]Cl₂ COMPLEXES

Complexes	Colour*	m.p. (dec.)† (°C)	Reaction time (hr)	Yield (%)	Analysis, Found(Calcd.) (%)			
					C	H	N	Cl
[(C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₁ NH ₂)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	Golden- Yellow	96	2	55	41.2 (41.7)	4.0 (3.8)	6.8 (6.9)	23.2 (23.5)
[(C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₁ NH ₂)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	Golden- Yellow	81	2	52	41.4 (41.9)	3.6 (3.4)	6.9 (6.9)	23.2 (23.6)
[(C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₇ CH ₂ NH ₂)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	Greyish- Yellow	88	2.5	50	43.0 (43.3)	2.9 (2.7)	6.7 (6.8)	22.9 (23.3)
[(C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₁ N)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	Golden- Yellow	105	2	58	40.3 (40.8)	3.3 (3.2)	76.9 (.1)	23.8 (24.1)
[(C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₄ H ₉ NO)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	Golden- Yellow	90	2.5	50	38.5 (38.7)	3.0 (2.8)	7.0 (7.1)	23.9 (24.1)
[(C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₉ NH ₂)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	Yellowish- Grey	80	2.5	55	36.5 (37.0)	3.6 (3.4)	7.4 (7.6)	25.4 (25.7)
[(C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₁ NH ₂)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	Grey	78	3	50	39.1 (39.3)	4.0 (3.9)	7.1 (7.2)	24.1 (24.5)
[(C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₁ NH ₂)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	Yellowish- Grey	73	2.5	56	39.3 (39.5)	3.5 (3.6)	7.2 (7.2)	24.3 (24.6)
[(C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₇ CH ₂ NH ₂)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	Greyish- Yellow	60	2.5	53	40.6 (41.0)	3.1 (2.9)	7.0 (7.1)	24.0 (24.2)
[(C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₁ N)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	Yellowish- Grey	95	3	50	38.1 (38.3)	3.3 (3.3)	7.2 (7.4)	24.8 (25.1)
[(C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₄ H ₉ NO)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	Yellowish- Grey	101	2.5	54	35.8 (36.1)	3.1 (3.0)	7.3 (7.4)	24.9 (25.1)

* All the complexes were isolated as shining crystalline solids.

† Colour of the complexes lightened on heating.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF (L-L)(Am)MoCl₄ COMPLEXES

Complexes*	m.p. (dec.)† (°C)	Yield (%)	Magnetic moment (B.M.)	Analysis, Found(Calcd.) (%)			
				C	H	N	Cl
(C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₁ NH ₂)MoCl ₄	115	20	2.54	41.4(41.6)	4.5(4.4)	7.8(8.0)	27.0(27.8)
(C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₁ NH ₂)MoCl ₄	100	22	2.62	41.6(41.7)	4.2(4.0)	7.9(8.1)	27.0(27.4)
(C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₇ CH ₂ NH ₂)MoCl ₄	125	18	2.58	43.0(43.4)	3.3(3.2)	7.8(8.0)	26.5(27.0)
(C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₁ N)MoCl ₄	128	24	2.73	40.2(40.5)	3.6(3.7)	8.2(8.3)	27.8(28.2)
(C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₄ H ₉ NO)MoCl ₄	121	27	2.61	37.5(38.0)	3.4(3.3)	8.3(8.3)	27.8(28.1)
(C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₉ NH ₂)MoCl ₄	111	20	2.59	35.6(35.9)	4.2(4.0)	8.8(8.9)	30.1(30.4)
(C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₁ NH ₂)MoCl ₄	105	23	2.73	38.4(38.7)	4.7(4.6)	8.4(8.4)	28.3(28.6)
(C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₁ NH ₂)MoCl ₄	117	22	2.68	38.5(38.7)	4.3(4.2)	8.4(8.5)	28.4(28.8)
(C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₇ CH ₂ NH ₂)MoCl ₄	113	25	2.65	40.2(40.7)	3.5(3.3)	8.1(8.3)	27.6(28.3)
(C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₁ N)MoCl ₄	104	21	2.56	37.2(37.5)	4.0(3.9)	8.5(8.7)	29.3(29.6)
(C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₄ H ₉ NO)MoCl ₄	126	19	2.55	34.5(34.9)	3.5(3.5)	8.6(8.7)	29.1(29.5)

* All the complexes are yellow in colour.

† Colour of the complexes changed to brown on heating.

TABLE 3—MOLECULAR CONDUCTIVITY AND C-O STRETCHING FREQUENCIES OF [(L-L)(Am)Mo(CO)₃Cl]Cl₂ COMPLEXES

Complexes	Mol. Cond. (ohm ⁻¹ . cm ²)	ν _(C-O) (KBr discs) (cm ⁻¹)		
		2051	1975	1922
[(C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₉ NH ₂)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	65.5	2051(vs)	1975(vs)	1922(vs)
[(C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₁ NH ₂)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	52.3	2045(vs)	1976(vs)	1926(vs)
[(C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₁ NH ₂)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	65.8	2041(vs)	1970(vs)	1928(vs)
[(C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₇ CH ₂ NH ₂)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	51.0	2050(vs)	1968(vs)	1928(vs)
[(C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₁ N)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	61.6	2041(vs)	1965(vs)	1920(vs)
[(C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₄ H ₉ NO)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	49.5	2042(vs)	1970(vs)	1920(vs)
[(C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₉ NH ₂)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	60.3	2048(vs)	1972(vs)	1921(vs)
[(C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₁ NH ₂)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	58.1	2048(vs)	1970(vs)	1920(vs)
[(C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₁ NH ₂)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	49.9	2041(vs)	1965(vs)	1923(vs)
[(C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₇ CH ₂ NH ₂)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	42.6	2045(vs)	1975(vs)	1928(vs)
[(C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₁ N)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	55.3	2050(vs)	1975(vs)	1925(vs)
[(C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂)(C ₄ H ₉ NO)Mo(CO) ₃ Cl]Cl ₂	58.8	2042(vs)	1972(vs)	1920(vs)

the region 2051-1920 cm⁻¹ (Table 3). Shifting of these bands to higher region (~160 cm⁻¹) when compared to their parent carbonyls⁴ was probably due to coordination of chlorine to molybdenum.

Appearance of three strong bands in the carbonyl region indicated the presence of three carbonyl groups in *cis*-position. Except for minor variation, nature and region of the bands were similar to

analogous mixed amine bromo complexes² and tritertiaryarsine substituted molybdenum (or tungsten) tricarbonyl halides^{5,6}. Other bands that appeared at *ca.* 3350-3320 m(br) cm⁻¹ and 1620 (m), 1570(ms) cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν (N-H) and its deformations vibrations respectively (due to amine).

The absorptions at *ca.* 1608 (w), 1593 (ms), 1490(s), 1420 (vs), 1336 (mw) cm⁻¹ in [(*o*-phen)(Am)-Mo(CO)₃Cl]Cl₃ derivatives and at *ca.* 1596 (vs), 1560 (s), 1435 (vs), 1240 (w) cm⁻¹ in [(2,2'-bipy)-(Am)Mo(CO)₃Cl]Cl₃ derivatives may be attributed to the characteristic vibrations of *o*-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl⁷ respectively.

Magnetic susceptibility measurement of [(L-L)-(Am)Mo(CO)₃Cl]Cl₃ complexes at room temperature showed their diamagnetism and molar conductance in the range 42.6-65.5 ohm⁻¹ cm² (Table 3) demonstrated their uni-univalent ionic nature in nitrobenzene. The rather high values of molar conductance in nitrobenzene solution were probably due to the coordination of solvent molecules⁸ and partial dissociation of complexes to some more ionic species in the solution. These evidences indicated that the complexes were likely to be seven coordinated derivatives of molybdenum(II). Chlorine outside the coordination sphere may be supposed to act as trichloride anion, Cl₃⁻¹, as in several metal carbonyl halide complexes reported earlier^{2,9-12}.

(L-L)(Am)MoCl₄ complexes were yellow crystalline solids, moderately soluble in aromatic hydrocarbons and polar solvents. On exposure to air or in solutions they decomposed to sticky masses. However, they were much more stable than the above mentioned chlorocarbonyls. On heating in sealed capillary tubes, they were first converted to brown (unidentified) products which on further heating decomposed to black masses and then melted at high temperatures.

Infrared spectra of (*o*-phen)(Am)MoCl₄ complexes exhibited N-H stretching and deformation bands at *ca.* 3360-3340 m(br) cm⁻¹ and 1622 (m), 1575 (m) cm⁻¹ respectively. Characteristic bands of *o*-phenanthroline⁷ appeared at *ca.* 1611 (w), 1597(m), 1490 (s), 1424 (s), 1340 (w) cm⁻¹. Absorptions attributable to terminal or bridging C-O were absent.

In the infrared spectra of (2,2'-bipy)(Am)MoCl₄ complexes, bands at *ca.* 3370-3362 m(br) cm⁻¹ and 1610 (w), 1565 (m) cm⁻¹ may be assigned to N-H stretching and deformation frequencies respectively. Bands observed at *ca.* 1596 (s), 1567 (m), 1435 (s), 1262 m(w) cm⁻¹ may be attributed to characteristic vibrations of 2,2'-bipyridyl⁷. Absence of bands in C-O stretching region indicated that they did not contain carbonyl groups.

All the (L-L)(Am)MoCl₄ complexes were found to be non-ionic in nitrobenzene (molar conductance <1 ohm⁻¹ cm²). Magnetic moment data in the range 2.54-2.73 B.M. (Table 2) indicated the paramagnetic nature of the complexes similar to their recently prepared mixed amine bromo analogues² and halophosphine complexes, (PMe₂Ph)₃-MX₄ (M=Mo, W and X=Cl, Br), of hepta-coordinated M(IV), reported in literature¹³.

Acknowledgement

Author is indebted to Dr. P. P. Singh, M.L.K. College, Balrampur (U.P.) for his valuable suggestions and to the authorities of C.D.R.I., Lucknow and I.I.T., Kanpur for providing spectral and microanalytical results. Facilities provided by Prof. R. P. Rastogi and Dr. S. C. Tripathi to carry out part of the work at Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur are greatly appreciated.

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